

EXPLAINING WISDOM WORDS IN MOTHER LANGUAGE LESSONS WITH THE HELP OF DICTIONARIES

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Abstract : In the article of students speech in cultivation mother language of science place open given

Key words : Method , competence , wisdom words , discussion , grammar , education , technology .

In our country our future successors to be to young people innovative , advanced methods and methods support , modern pedagogical from technologies using education to give and of students in education quality efficiency to raise young people competitive by doing bring up education system in front of standing main task Uzbekistan " To the youth " of September 14, 2016 about state policy "about". Law , Uzbekistan Republic President of February 7, 2017 " Uzbekistan Republic more development according to Action strategy on" No. PF-4947, Ministers " General medium and medium special , profession of education state education standards confirmation on" Decision No. 187 of April 29, 2019 " Uzbekistan Republic the people education system development until 2030 concept confirmation on" in Decrees No. PF-5712 defined row tasks of students linguistic and speech competencies to develop the ground prepares " Uzbekistan Republic more development according to Actions strategy". set given " independent thoughtful , firm vital the point look have , to the Motherland loyal young people education , democratic reforms deepening and citizenship society development in the process their social activity increase " task school age of students independent thinking potential expansion radical reforms at the core developing in our country active , searching and time with breathless to be requirement is enough Mother tongue from teaching goal of the tongue society members between which performs mother that's it task - students thought statement to do to the activity preparation from the task come comes out Because people own activities all in the fields each other with active in relation will be They are always themselves wrapping received material in existence things and events about thought they walk and own thoughts to each other known they do

The language to know his grammar laws and regulations , definition mastery only not but mother from the rich possibilities of the language practical use to know is also the idea oral and written in the form right , understandable and literate express is to know . To this reach for mother language in their classes dictionary on to work separately attention focus it is necessary Because in the textbook given assignment and in the texts students for you don't understand was words , sentences meeting stands Wise words assignments during when we read , of course , to the dictionary appeal we do East of scholars purmano thoughts from generation to generation passed and polished more stronger to the effect have is happening In the past living past scientists , senior life to the experience have made great people wise words of students wise is a companion . Others from the word different respectively , this

words as if thirsty to hearts is life . Wise words through in life occurring to problems easy solution to find about imagination wake up need Hazrat Alisher Navoi : "If wisdom to learn if you seek , wisdom if you love , your life Noah the prophet like a lifetime long " Let it be , " they said .

Mind to evil if you look at it , it's a person sly . sly , deceitful be remains . (Abu Nasr Farabi)

This is it wise the word mother language 5th grade in class to the student explanation for dictionary with work need Uzbek of the language explanatory as follows in the dictionary explained : RAZIL [Arabic : lowly , pallid ; immoral , corrupt] 1. A person repulsive ; naughty , vile , low , abysmal . 2. Manfur , accursed .

MAKKOR [Arabic : cunning , trickster (man) 1. Makr - a trick Master : 2. Trick - a trick based on crafty Wise words with while we are working the following aspects importance focus need :

1. **Students stranger words with introduction** Students in the textbook to words the first times face coming to be can This is the word new appear has been word if not , the reader his the meaning does not know , so the student for new word is considered to words face they come Such don't speak the meaning synonyms cause expand the way with , opposite meaningful words with comment to give the way with , make a sentence through the meaning solution , pictures through concept harvest to do the way with explanation can Such work in students word to the meanings relatively sensitivity surface brings

2. **Students of the word new meanings with introduction** Many p cases of the word content in determining in the word phonetic changes difficulty gives birth Languages from observation as it is known , morphological indicators either independent meaningful from lexemes , or each different of additions mutually united new addition harvest to do method is formed . Many words by joining leaving as a result second part to a morpheme turning around leaving can :

This is in the 5th grade textbook a lot occurs .

3. Some in places wise of words content more complete understanding for different use of games as well possible

Alisher Navoi's wise words :

Polite a person all of people It's good , everyone nations for it's nice Etiquette small the elderly adults to his prayer deserves does

Young people are blessed for life enjoy will be (" Instructive from "stories "

Games through national from our values , Uzbek from our heritage using , dignity , kindness , manners , parents and adults respect to do such as qualities to the child's heart absorb can For example : in the game " Polite Boy". class to the group divided into har from the group one student participation is enough

Teacher : - Well children , good boy , get up in the morning standing up what will do ."

Teacher : - A polite child is early early stand up , body education does , father - greets his mother and family members.

Student : - What a polite boy hello gives ?

Teacher : " Hello I say hello gives , then breakfast does

Teacher : - A polite child at the table around how sits .

Teacher : - A polite child is one of the adults below sits , " Bismillohir merciful rahim " to the table from adults after hand transmits in his mouth food with does not speak

Like this from questions and answers after groups the answer annotated and collected scores are posted and encouraged.

This kind of lesson-game type of training children prepares for hard work, their independent, creative activity, increases vocabulary and helps to develop speech and strengthens the coherence of lessons.

So, in every lesson, no matter what subject it is

However, our first task is to achieve conscious, fluent, correct and expressive reading of the students, and to try to develop their speech.

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